

Antun Andrić¹
Hrvatski operator prijenosnog sustava d.o.o.
antun.andric@hops.hr

Biljana Ivanović
Crnogorski elektroprenosni sistem A.D.
biljana.ivanovic@cges.me

Obrad Škrba
Nezavisni operator sistema u BiH
o.skrba@nosbih.ba

MOGUĆNOSTI PRIMJENE INOVATIVNIH PROIZVODA U ELEKTROENERGETSKOM SUSTAVU BUDUĆNOSTI – PROJEKT CROSSBOW

SAŽETAK

Europski elektroenergetski sustav, pa tako i sustavi pojedinih zemalja kao njegov integralni dio u procesu je transformacije od tradicionalnog, u velikoj mjeri centraliziranog, utemeljenog na fosilnim gorivima prema novom, decentraliziranom i utemeljenom na niskougljičnim tehnologijama. Uvažavajući gore navedeno, operatori sustava HOPS, NOS BIH i CGES su pristupili CROSSBOW projektu (engl. „CROSS BOrder management of variable renewable energies and storage units enabling a transnational Wholesale market“) koji je financiran iz okvira Horizon 2020. U radu će se prezentirati razvijeni inovativni produkti o okviru CROSSBOW projekta, izložiti će se dio rezultata preliminarnih ispitivanja.

Ključne riječi: uravnoteženje sustava, obnovljivi izvori energije, niskougljična strategija

INNOVATIVE PRODUCTS IN THE FUTURE POWER SYSTEM - CROSSBOW PROJECT

ABSTRACT

European power system, as well as related national power systems are transforming from traditional, centralized and fossil fuel oriented power system, towards new, decentralized with a cornerstone in renewable energy sources. Path of this transition is challenging for transmission system operators (TSOs), taking into account an obligation that system security must be secured all the time. Taking into account above-mentioned TSOs, HOPS, NOS BiH and CGES with other partners, are participating in CROSSBOW project („CROSS BOrder management of variable renewable energies and storage units enabling a transnational Wholesale market“) financed by European Union Horizon 2020 framework. In this paper innovative CROSSBOW products will be presented as well as part of preliminary demonstration results.

¹ Stavovi izneseni u referatu su osobna mišljenja autora, nisu obvezujući za poduzeće/instituciju u kojoj je autor zaposlen te se ne moraju nužno podudarati sa službenim stavovima poduzeća / institucije.

Key words: power system balancing, renewable energy sources, low-carbon strategy

1. INTRODUCTION

European power system, as well as related national power systems are transforming from traditional, centralized and fossil fuel oriented power system, towards new, decentralized with a cornerstone in renewable energy sources. As a result of the energy transition, lot of challenges but also opportunities occurred in energy sector, for both market parties and the TSOs, e.g. system adequacy, system balancing, congestion management which are the challenges that have to be solved, based on their impact, either locally or regionally or on a level of entire interconnection. Taking into account above-mentioned, TSOs, HOPS, NOS BiH and CGES with other partners, are participating in CROSSBOW project („CROSS BOrder management of variable renewable energies and storage units enabling a transnational Wholesale market“) financed by European Union Horizon 2020 framework.

In this paper innovative CROSSBOW products will be presented as well as part of preliminary demonstration results. TSO challenges in the region, as a result of energy transition will be presented. Finally, several CROSSBOW demonstrations will be presented and analysed. General comments related to possible implementation are given when integrate research and development project and TSO work where system security must be secured all the time within available budget.

2. CROSSBOW PRODUCTS

2.1. General

CROSSBOW is a transmission system operator driven project with two interrelated and equally important strategic goals [1][4]. On the one hand, it aims at the successful deployment of set of technological solutions which enable increasing the shared use of resources to foster transmission networks cross-border management of variable renewable energy systems (RES) and storage units, while making possible a higher penetration of clean energies. While on the other hand, it aims to reduce network operational costs and improving economic benefits of RES and storage units. Since the project demonstrates a number of different technologies offering TSOs increased grid flexibility and robustness through: a) a better control of cross-border balancing energy at interconnection points; b) new storage solutions (distributed and centralized), offering ancillary services to operate Virtual Storage Plants (VSP); c) better ICT and communications (e.g. better network observability, enabling flexible generation and Demand Response schemas); d) the definition of a transnational wholesale market, proposing fair and sustainable remuneration for clean energies though the definition of new business models supporting the participation of new players (i.e. aggregators) and the reduction of costs.

2.1.1 ROC-BC

Regional Operation Centre Balancing Cockpit (ROC-BC) extends the functionalities of the already established at SCC premises, or yet under development by Regional Security Coordinator (RSC) initiatives, and proposes a set of tools for regional management and operation to enhance existing regional structures. In particular, current RSC functionalities include:

- Improved individual grid model (IGM) / Common grid model (CGM) delivery
- Coordinated security analysis
- Coordinated capacity calculation
- Outage planning coordination
- Short-term adequacy forecasts

CROSSBOW aims at explicitly addressing the development of balancing functionalities of future ROCs and their integration to existing RSCs. To this effect the project produces a ROC balancing cockpit that includes the ability of day-ahead and/or intraday determination of regional balancing capacity as well as the ability of facilitating the procurement of available balancing services by the TSOs. Furthermore, it acts

as a facilitator for the development of the toolkit for the integration of balancing markets in the region. In addition, other products of the project such as the DSM integration platform and the wholesale and ancillary markets toolkit can affect the core functions of RSCs and future ROCs. These functions of ROCs that can be affected by transnational market and demand side management are day-ahead adequacy forecast, coordinated security analysis, coordinating capacity calculation and outage planning coordination. Therefore, CROSSBOW addresses the impact of its products to the aforementioned ROC's services and tackles the issue of enhancing those in order to facilitate their integration in future ROCs.

2.1.2 RES-CC

RES Regional Coordination Centre (RES-CC) follows the examples of already existing national RES Control Centres, acting between TSO and RES producers. CROSSBOW proposes a Regional Coordination Centre platform to: 1) provide real-time supervision and control; 2) manage incidents in real time, speeding up their correction, either remotely or in coordination with local services, and achieving higher availability rates for installations; 3) support electric power management, sending the systems operators in the region and the ROC the production forecasts; 4) interact with the operators and ROC, sending real-time data on each generation facility, which enables the calculation of the electric power production that can be sent to the grid and maximize the contribution of RES to the system; and 5) provide data recording, analysis to optimize the availability and efficiency of the installations, substations and HV lines to guarantee the delivery of the energy generated.

2.1.3 RES-DU

Hybrid RES Dispatchable Unit (RES-DU) integrates non-dispatchable and dispatchable RES along with energy storage units under an advanced control system based on firm hybrid power plants connected to the transmission and distribution grids in a single Point of Common Coupling. The combination of non-dispatchable RES, such as wind and PV, with dispatchable RES, such as biogas, biomass or pumped hydro, and along with energy storage capability, through flow batteries and Lithium-ion batteries, leads to provision of more secure, stable and cleaner electricity supply thanks to flexible generation and enhanced grid stability.

CROSSBOW proves that it is possible to create a flexible architecture capable to incorporate new technologies or combinations of technologies. As a test case, a concept comprising dispatchable RES and conventional units (Hybrid RES dispatchable units) are able to follow a variable power schedule and meet TSOs requirements in terms of power, voltage, frequency, etc. The objective of this approach is to take advantage of synergies between different kind of renewable energy and energy storage technologies in order to optimise investments and increase the competitiveness of RES. This solution will meet the requirements imposed by TSOs to be considered as a dispatchable, firm and fully-flexible power plant and will substitute the current role of fossil fuel backup systems while increasing RES power generation.

2.1.4 STO-CC

STO-CC is the CROSSBOW product that proposes a novel Regional Storage Coordination Centre (STO-CC) to foster the cross-border usage of electrical energy storage infrastructure, since storage units, analogously to RES, require specific real-time monitoring and control, especially when they become relevant to the operation of transmission networks. Therefore, STO-CC has to provide real-time supervision and control, incident management, seamless interaction with system operators and optimisation of installations' performance. This approach is targeted to use electrical energy storage to reduce problems in the electricity grids resulting from increased deployment of renewable energy generation and thus enables a higher penetration and more efficient usage of renewable energies in the South-East European (SEE) region.

2.1.5 VSP

A Virtual Storage Plant (VSP) is a platform capable of integrating the characteristics and limitations of distributed individual storage units – using the same or different storage technologies – while maximizing their performance and reducing additional costs stemming from not-optimal usage. By processing the grid data obtained from the real-time grid monitoring, the platform autonomously recognizes grid congestions and releases available power from the pooled storage systems. With the so-called Virtual Storage Plant, redispatch measures can be avoided. Moreover, the platform enables the participation in transnational wholesale and ancillary markets. Thus, the energy storage systems can participate in the primary frequency control, the secondary frequency control, the tertiary frequency control and intraday energy markets. Furthermore, it can contribute to transmission deferral and distribution deferral services.

The VSP platform features intelligent algorithms that derive the optimal set of units running. Here the current grid state, generation and demand forecasts as well as the status and characteristics of different storage types are considered. In order to aggregate and manage the vast amount of storage units efficiently, ICT infrastructures based on current standards will have to be established. For demonstration purposes a controlled environment emulating parts of the transmission grid and its corresponding underlying grid levels are compiled. The setup also features several small-scale battery storage units so that the interaction between the grid and the batteries can be analysed in real-time. In addition to the controlled environment for chemical storage, the VSP platform will also manage the existing pumped hydro assets in Bulgaria and Serbia.

2.1.6 WAMAS

The WAMAS product (Wide Area Monitoring and Awareness System) consists of an advanced real-time central system and a number of time synchronised acquisition units. The system will be used for real-time data exchange between TSOs, DSOs, RESs and storage devices and provides information about storage availability, congestions, and warnings when e.g. power system operates close to the limits, etc. It will also perform control actions to maintain stable operation of the power system. The goal is to ensure the stable power system operation with the integration of RES and storages in dynamic electricity market conditions. Data is exploited from the existing systems from TSO and DSO centres (from SCADA systems), PMU devices, smart meters and other devices like RTUs. Measurements and algorithms will coordinate RES and storages, assuring stable power system operation under dynamic market conditions.

The purpose of WAMAS will be to show the influence of the market actions and RES on the power system stability and dynamics. With a higher real-time resolution metering it will be possible to evaluate the direct impact on electricity market and RES penetration limits, providing the grid with power system dynamics and awareness capabilities in case of operation of the power system close to the stability limits. In this respect, the project will take advantage of particular WAMAS applications, such as event recording, real-time monitoring, phasor-assisted state estimating, real-time congestion management, and recognition of instabilities.

2.1.7 DSM-IP

The Demand Side Management Integration Platform (DSM-IP), comprises communication interfaces for monitoring and control of dispatchable (flexible) loads, advanced algorithms for the integration of DSM in the improvement of cross-border power flows and network operability, interfaces with other Regional Control Centres (RES-CC, STO-CC and ROC), interfaces with the TSO-DSO coordination platform, and applications for the business and market actors. The development of these functionalities will consider existing standards used in the region as well as special requirements by the local TSOs, DSOs and demand side participants.

CROSSBOW investigates the effect of DSM actions on overall network steady state and dynamic operation at both the load reduction and recovery times, and the extent and potential that shifting of different types of load from one hour to the other can have on overall network performance (steady state and dynamic) and cross-border power exchange. When analysing the effect of DSM not only the portion of available controllable and non-controllable demand at different times should be considered, but also and very importantly the nature and composition of controllable demand in terms of type of load categories (e.g., induction motors, constant power loads, constant impedance loads) available for DSM. Therefore,

CROSBOW develops a framework and algorithms that will provide clear guidance and methodology to deploy advanced DSM to facilitate increased cross-border power transfer at national and transnational level while ensuring at all times network voltage, angular and frequency stability.

2.1.8 CFP

The Cooperative Ownership of Flexibility Assets (CFP) supports an innovative cooperative business model that can be exploited to increase the penetration of RES and distributed energy resources. The platform is envisaged as a tool that should avoid the need for a business aggregator in the process of provision of ancillary services from groups of small flexibility assets. Furthermore, this platform will be aligned with existing regulation and general enough to support existing flexibility assets like Virtual Power Plants and Demand Response systems. It will also have an additional group of functionalities, such as democratic governance and payment services, that should eliminate the need of an aggregator as a separate subject on an enterprise level, to foster the self-management of the assets and the active users' empowerment.

Technical specifications for the CFP were made with the aim to ease further development in the second demonstrative task. The platform will be specified following a modular software architecture approach where each module will represent one functionality. This approach enables individual customers to select their own set of modules that fits to their particular use cases. The technologies, methodologies and flexibility platform tools will be used to develop new and enhance the existing flexibility platform modules.

2.1.9 AM

The Wholesale and Ancillary Market Toolset (AM) is set to propose a novel market design for ancillary services and wholesale electricity market aligned with the latest grid code and market development to enhance the integration of RES and DR. Through the CROSSBOW market platform, it will be demonstrated the impact of those technologies on enhancing the efficiency, transparency, scalability, interoperability, security and resilience of the market platform.

The market definition at CROSSBOW involves three different aspects: market design, market platform and cooperative ownership of flexibility assets. Current wholesale electricity and ancillary markets were designed for the incumbent technologies. The market rules and consequently the technical requirements are therefore often the ones that are limiting the participation of the RES, DR and storage on the markets. Another barrier is also that these market rules are different across the countries, and this prevents transnational participation of flexibility assets on the neighbouring markets.

3. TSO CHALLENGES

Region South East Europe is characterized by meshed network, small TSOs, with volatile network conditions mostly related to hydrology. In recent years, large RES integration is ongoing together with market development. Several challenges, as shown in picture 1 have been recognised by TSOs which was the main driver for the participation in the CROSSBOW project:

- System balancing: market based reserve procurement, balancing energy procurement, avoiding of the RES curtailment,
- Congestion management: redispatching,
- System Adequacy.

Picture 1: TSO challenges during transition of energy sector

Picture 1 shows main challenges for TSOs in the region. RES volatility may cause lack of reserves, voltage problems, grid overloads, RES curtailment. As network is meshed, TSOs tools and actions have to be aligned and coordinated. CROSSBOW assesses some of these problems through high level use cases (HLU) where real challenges and problems are assessed, solved by several developed CROSSBOW products which are, where it is possible, deployed and demonstrated (Picture 2). Detailed list of use cases could be found in [3].

Picture 2. Example: High level use case and CROSSBOW products

Moreover, besides TSOs problems and challenges, CROSSBOW assesses regional integration, through regional centre functionalities and innovative regional approaches looking for the synergies which may solve explicit problems more efficiently compared with the business as usual approach, as well as innovative concepts such as Virtual Storage Plant (VSP) or Cooperative ownership of Flexibility Assets (CFA) which may facilitate flexibility market development bringing new potential participants into it. With new participants for balancing and redispatching it may be expected that market impact would be beneficial for the whole community.

4. CROSSBOW PRELIMINARY DEMONSTRATION

In this chapter several, among almost fifty, preliminary demonstration experiments will be presented and analysed. (Table 1 - 3) [5].

Table 1. Curtailment distribution in the area of the southern border between Croatia and Bosnia & Herzegovina, preliminary experiment

Preliminary / Final	This experiment covers a different scenario where the system operator identifies a region whose RES production may be curtailed and the curtailment amount, and passes this limitation to the RES-CC. With this limitation in mind, the RES-CC optimal curtailment algorithms aim to obtain the best operation point for the RES parks in a region, regarding the limitations imposed by the SO. This mechanism is easier to implement by the system operator, because the curtailment details are calculated by the RES-CC. Normally the system operator identifies the regions by a representing substation (normally a 400kv or 220kv substation). In the particular scenario of Bosnian-Croatian border, the regions selected to test will be the substations of Konjsko and Mostar.
Timeframe	Problem is identified for a period of 1 hour in the upcoming 24h. The test will simulate the effect of RES energy curtailment in the affected area and present the resulting power flow measurements after the corrective actions are simulated. The SO could use this as a way of testing the effect of different corrective action before applying in real
Targets	honouring grid limitations by manually curtailing renewable energy generation.
Actors	TSO (HOPS & NOSBiH), RSC (SCC), RES manager (simulated)
Crossbow products	WAMAS, RES-CC
Assets & systems	HOPS SCADA, NOSBiH SCADA
Description of the experiment	<p>. The process is the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The WAMAS tool will present the operator with updated information about current and forecasted network status: Power flows, voltages, topology status, etc. Problematic situations are highlighted so that the operator can easily notice about them. Different views will be provided to help the operators better understand the problems. 2) The operator will select in this interface different substations in the region (Konjsko and /or Mostar) and will specify for them production limitations based on their expertise and knowledge. The aim of the actions will be to solve the identified problems. 3) The actions could be marked for immediate execution, or scheduled for a future period. At the appropriate time, activation of the actions will be sent to the RES-CC, that will reply confirming the reception. WAMAS interface will present operator with the successful (or not) reception of the message by RES-CC. 4) The RES-CC will analyze the limitation and will distribute it to the portfolio of assets according to the five identified strategies. three different solutions will be generated 5) KPIs will be generated to evaluate the impact by applying the five different algorithms considered for the distribution. The KPIs will be accessible in the RES-CC user interface 6) The system operator will activate these mechanisms several times during the testing period so that the KPI's are properly filled and conclusions can be extracted from the application of the different algorithms <p>For this scenario, we will not have direct control of any RES asset in the region, because of the economic impact of the application of the actions, nevertheless the impact of the actions could be analysed and compared against the actions taken by the operators.</p>

Picture 3. List of generators in the area of Konjsko substation in RES-CC user interface and distribution of curtailment according to uniform distribution algorithm

Table 2. Voltage regulation with cross-border DSM, preliminary experiment

Preliminary / Final	Preliminary - done			
Timeframe	July 2020			
Targets	Exploring the extent to which the existing DSM capacity could be used for managing system voltage profile.			
Actors	CGES			
Crossbow products	DSM-IP			
Assets & systems	Aluminium smelter - KAP; 400 kV line Podgorica 2 – Lastva, Podgorica 2 – Ribarevine, Podgorica 2 – Pec, Lastva – Trebinje, SCADA (CGES)			
Description of the experiment	Measurements of P, Q, V were performed for one hour (6:00 to 7:00) in two consecutive days, where in the first day DSM asset was disconnected, and in the second one it was connected. A disturbance (disconnection of line Podgorica 2 – Lastva) was performed both days at 6:30, to record the power response of the lines surrounding the disconnected line, primarily the tie lines.			
	Date	DSM Action	Disturbance	Recording Period
	06/07/2020 (Monday)	Largest consumer KAP fully disconnected (With DSM)	Disconnection of line PG2 – Lastva at 6:30	6:00 – 7:00
	07/07/2020 (Tuesday)	Largest consumer KAP fully operated (Without DSM)	Disconnection of line PG2 – Lastva at 6:30	6:00 – 7:00

Picture 4. Impact on Voltage (in Per Unit) of Tie Line Lastva – Trebinje (LAS-TRE) and Line Lastva – Podgorica 2(LAS-PG2) during Experiment Period Measured at Lastva

Table 3. “Rent“ storage unit for temporary storage of surplus energy (cross-bordering)

Preliminary / Final	<p>The test case refers to curtailment alleviation by the usage of energy storage. This use case requires the close cooperation of RES-CC, STO-CC and AM.</p> <p>For testing these use cases, the RES-CC and the STO-CC will be used. The experiment will try to identify situations where curtailment is happening or could happen. The curtailment could be voluntary or involuntary. Involuntary mean imposed by the system operator linked to some security problem identified, whilst the voluntary may be related to low prices due to excess of demand.</p> <p>This test case covers for the voluntary curtailment. In this case, there could be options to alleviate the curtailment by storing the energy instead of curtail them, and later on obtain a surplus based on the money earned by the energy storage asset when selling the energy at higher price. This is a kind of RES production shifting to more convenient periods (energy arbitrage).</p>
Timeframe	The algorithms will be running continuously during the demonstration period
Targets	<p>The assets considered will be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - As storage assets: the hydro pumped energy storage in Bajina Basta and the VARTA batteries deployed in Zagreb laboratory - As renewable units, the whole renewable portfolio used in RES-CC
Actors	Energy storage owner, renewable producer
Crossbow products	STO-CC, RES-CC, AM
Assets & systems	Bajina Basta SCADA interfaced by STO-CC, Varta batteries deployed in Zagreb laboratory, all the dispatching centres and assets handled by RES-CC
Description of the experiment	<p>The steps for this test case could be summarized as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) RES-CC periodically tries to sell the forecasted energy in the market. 2) After a market period is closed, it may happen that not all the energy has been sold. This can happen because of different reasons: The demand may be too low or the trading prices may be lower than the production cost. 3) If the amount of energy not allocated in the market (and thus, non-generable) is higher than a certain threshold, RES-CC will try to store it in an energy storage asset. 4) RES-CC will bid in the Storage market for the surplus of energy. The bidding price will be the production cost. 5) STO-CC will periodically check this market and if there are bids that can be accepted, buying bids are submitted to apply for these bids. 6) In case more than one RES is submitting bids, the cheapest bids will be selected first. This will promote competition. 7) For the RES units whose bids get accepted, they can go to the wholesale market and safely sell their energy at a price of zero. STO-CC will go to Wholesale market and buy the same amount of energy at the best possible price. 8) At the appropriate time, RES units will produce the energy and storage units will store the acquired energy. 9) STO-CC will later sell the stored energy in a more beneficial period in terms of price.

	<p>10) The gap between the amount of money obtained by RES units in the wholesale market (near to zero) and the price they offer to the storage market is compensated from the money obtained by STO-CC. The surplus is also paying the cost of storage.</p> <p>This mechanism allows the RES units to, at least, be paid for the energy by the production cost, and the storage units obtain cheap energy that they can sell better in other periods. Also, social welfare is enhanced by the price curve smoothing. This mechanism is done by specific python processes at both the RES-CC and STO-CC premises. The Crossbow AM product allows defining different markets for energy trading. The RES-CC and STO-CC cooperation for energy arbitrage will be based on a storage market in the AM. In this market, only renewable and energy storage units are allowed to participate, because the aim of such market is to help renewables reduce the energy curtailment and obtain new sources of income by trading resources in competition, relieving the need of subsidies and premium tariffs. Since energy storage is a scarce resource, the storage market will promote competition among renewable units in the whole region.</p>
--	---

Looking into above-mentioned experiments it may be seen that wide range of activities has been demonstrated and planned to be demonstrated during CROSSBOW project. Products which bring a lot of savings, either on side of system security, either on financial side (e.g. savings) have the highest potential for implementation in the TSOs. Innovative concepts, (e.g. rent of storage capacity versus RES curtailment) far from current practice, may help TSOs in everyday business. The main challenge will be how to integrate these innovative concepts into regular electricity markets among affected regional TSOs. For example, renting a storage by TSOs, beside its logical background is not foreseen among current balancing mechanisms. Thereof, legal framework should be adopted by affected parties.

5. CONCLUSION

Crossbow project is currently in demonstration phases. Several products have been developed and deployed as described in Chapter 2. Chapter 3 describes expectations from TSOs which challenges related to the system balancing, congestion management, system adequacy as well as market integration and development. These problems will be assessed by CROSSBOW products through demonstration using several products coupled in high level use cases. Three preliminary demonstrations have been selected for this symposium. Products which bring lot of savings, either on side of system security, either on financial side (e.g. savings) have the highest potential for implementation in the TSOs. The main challenge will be how to integrate these innovative concepts into regular electricity markets among affected regional TSOs. For example, renting a storage by TSOs, beside its logical background is not foreseen among current balancing mechanisms. Thereof, for some ideas legal framework should be adopted by affected parties.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This paper is a result of the authors research conducted within the CROSSBOW project. The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 773430.

7. LITERATURE

- [1] CROSSBOW (CROSS BOrder management of variable renewable energies and storage units enabling a transnational Wholesale market), Available: <http://crossbowproject.eu/>
- [2] Zora Luburić, Tonči Tadin, Antun Andrić, Jelena Ponoćko, Mengxuan Wang Jovica V. Milanović, Obrad Škrba, Bojan Rebić: Provision of the experiments by coordination of demand side response units in the region of southeast europe within the crossbow project - HOPS case, HRO CIGRE 2020,
- [3] D2.2 CROSSBOW Use cases, scenarios and KPIs identification, available: <http://crossbowproject.eu>

- [4] D12.1 Integration and deployment of CROSSBOW ecosystem, available: <http://crossbowproject.eu>
- [5] D13.2 CROSSBOW integrated ecosystem preliminary demonstration, available: <http://crossbowproject.eu>